

AI-Driven Triage for External Eye Diseases: A Deep Learning and LLM Approach for Community Vision Care

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Abstract. In many primary care and emergency settings, the limited experience or education regarding ophthalmic conditions often leads to over-referral for benign or self-limiting external eye conditions, resulting in unnecessary specialist utilization and delayed treatment for patients with more severe ocular diseases. Our study aims to develop and evaluate a novel tool that integrates a deep learning model with a large language model (LLM) to classify common external eye conditions using a simple photograph of the eye from a cell phone. This tool will provide tailored resources for treatment, warning signs to watch for (triage), and recommendations for follow-up care.

We utilized a publicly available dataset on external eye disease classification (Bitto & Ahmed, 2024) to train and evaluate deep learning models, including MobileNet, ResNet-18, and EfficientNet, for multilabel classification of external eye diseases, including cataracts, conjunctivitis, uveitis, palpebral, and standard eye images (Figure 1). Following SMOTE class rebalancing and stratified K-fold cross-validation, EfficientNet demonstrated the strongest performance, achieving an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) of 0.9987, an accuracy of 97.61%, and an F1 score of 0.9762. These high-confidence predictions were then used to prompt Llama 3.1 8B Turbo LLM to generate personalized resources for the identified condition (Figure 2).

By linking the recognition of disease presentation to the generation of tailored resources, this framework aims to reduce barriers to timely care and enhance patient outcomes in ophthalmology. Unlike previous OCT classification studies, binary models, our model addresses the broader public health challenge of triage and education at the community level, reducing barriers to care and promoting earlier intervention in ophthalmology.

Keywords: Ophthalmology, AI in Healthcare, External Eye Disease.

1 Introduction

Over-referral to vision specialists for eye complaints is a significant challenge in community and primary care settings, particularly in areas with limited access to ophthalmologists. Many patients present to primary care providers, school nurse offices, and urgent care clinics with complaints of blurry vision, irritation, redness, and discharge, and consequently, due to limited ophthalmologic training in medicine, are referred to eye specialists “just in case.” While the intent behind these actions is driven by caution, the reality is that most of these referrals are for benign, self-limiting conditions[1].

The unfortunate consequence of these actions, however, is multifaceted. By 2035, it's anticipated that the field of ophthalmology's supply of practitioners will fail to meet the demand of their patients by 30%[2]. The problem is only exacerbated by unnecessary referrals clogging ophthalmology clinics, increasing wait times, and delaying care for those with vision-threatening conditions. Patients and families may face costs, missed work or school, and anxiety over specialist appointments that may not be needed, or worse, in those with critical pathologies, delayed appointments, and poor outcomes. For healthcare systems, these referrals represent a significant and avoidable burden.

There is a critical need for low-cost, scalable tools that support accurate triage of external eye conditions in community settings—tools that can distinguish between a benign condition that can be managed at home with some patient education and watchful waiting, and those that require urgent specialist referral.

In this study, we present and evaluate a novel AI-powered triage tool that integrates a deep learning model with a large language model (LLM) to classify common external eye conditions using a simple photograph of the eye taken from a cell phone camera. Following identification of the disease, the tool will generate tailored, patient-facing resources using an LLM to provide tailored resources for treatment, warning signs to watch for, and recommendations for follow-up care.

2 Methods

2.1 Dataset and Preprocessing

We utilized the publicly available dataset titled "Image Dataset on Eye Diseases Classification (Uveitis, Conjunctivitis, Cataract, Eyelid) with Symptoms and SMOTE Validation [3]". The dataset consists of high-quality, labeled clinical images corresponding to five external eye conditions: conjunctivitis, cataract, uveitis, standard healthy eyes, and pathologies with a blepharal origin. Given the initial class imbalance inherent in medical image datasets, we applied the Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique (SMOTE) to augment the dataset across all condition categories. All images were resized to a uniform resolution of 224 x 224 pixels and normalized for input into pre-trained CNN architectures.

2.2 Model Training

We fine-tuned three CNN Models commonly used in image classification: MobileNet, ResNet-18, and EfficientNet-B0. These models were chosen not only for their proven performance but also for their suitability in low-latency, resource-constrained environments, a requirement for future deployment on mobile and web-based platforms.

Each model was then trained on multilabel classification with sigmoid-activated outputs to allow the detection of the multiple conditions presented in our dataset. A 5-fold stratified cross-validation approach was employed to introduce generalizability. Lastly, performance was measured using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC), accuracy, and F1 score.

2.3 LLM Integration

After determining the top-performing model, we coupled that model's output into Llama 3.1 8B Turbo, an advanced LLM, to generate personalized health information for the predicted condition. Prompts were templated to avoid a definitive medical diagnosis, instead focusing on relevant symptomatology, a brief explanation of the condition, home care recommendations, and warning signs that should prompt a visit to a specialist.

3 Results

3.1 Dataset and Preprocessing

Among the three models tested, EfficientNet-B0 demonstrated superior performance across all evaluation metrics. Notably, it achieved an AUROC of .9990, an accuracy of 0.9738, and an F1 of 0.9739. MobileNet and ResNet-18 also performed exceptionally well, but slightly fell short compared to EfficientNet. MobileNet achieved an AUROC of 0.9981, an accuracy of 0.9651, and an F1 of 0.9650, while ResNet-18 achieved an AUROC of 0.9988, an accuracy of 0.9651, and an F1 of 0.9645.

One-vs-Rest Multiclass evaluation of EfficientNet-B0 demonstrated strong identifying performance for individual external eye diseases. Achieving AUROC values of 0.9990 for cataract, 0.9998 for conjunctivitis, 0.9982 for blepharal pathologies, 1.0000 for normal eye presentations, and 0.9982 for uveitis (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. The AUROC curve for the EfficientNet model in a one-vs-rest multiclass classification, assessing its ability to identify specific external eye disease presentations: Cataract, Conjunctivitis, Uveitis, Normal, or if the pathology is palpebral rather than ocular related.

The consistently high values made EfficientNet a suitable classifier for integrating Llama 3.1 8B Turbo, to then generate personalized ocular health resources (**Figure 2**).

Sample Integration

Patient Photo:

Validated Prediction Model Photo Prediction:
Conjunctivitis

You are a highly trained automated assistant specializing in ophthalmology and external eye diseases. Your role is to respond empathetically to the user's photo and their predicted condition. You will provide a list of specific resources for treatment, outline warning signs to watch for, and make recommendations about when follow-up care may be necessary.

Avoid providing a medical diagnosis or suggesting certainty. Instead, focus on treatment recommendations and encourage seeking support if needed.

Personalized Metadata:

- Location: `{location}`*

Approved resources: `{approved_resources_list}`*

*to be dynamically replaced with real-time model predictions or metadata for each patient's photo

Hey There! Here's some friendly, easy-to-follow advice if you're dealing with something like pink eye (conjunctivitis):

****Here's what might help:****

- ****Keep things clean.**** Gently wipe away any crusty stuff around the eye with a clean cloth and warm water. Use a fresh part of the cloth each time—no double-dipping!
- ****Avoid poking or rubbing.**** It's super tempting, but touching the eye can spread the irritation or make it worse. Try to keep your hands busy elsewhere!
- ****Cool it down.**** A cold compress (like a clean washcloth with cold water) over the eye for a few minutes can soothe itchiness or swelling. Think of it as a mini spa treatment for your eye!
- ****Over-the-counter drops.**** Some drugstore eye drops can help ease discomfort, but skip ones that promise to "get the red out"—they might backfire. A pharmacist can steer you to the right kind.
- ****Rest and hydrate.**** Your body heals better when you're well-rested and drinking enough water.

****A few things to keep in mind:****

- Pink eye often gets better on its own in a few days, especially if it's caused by a virus (like a cold). But if it's not improving after 3-4 days or feels "really" painful, it might be time to chat with a healthcare provider.
- Wash your hands often, avoid sharing towels or pillowcases, and toss used tissues away right away. This helps keep others from catching it (if it's the contagious kind).
- If you wear contacts, give them a break until your eye feels better. They might trap irritants or slow healing.

****When to reach out for help:****

- If vision gets blurry, light feels too bright, or the eye gets swollen shut, don't wait—get checked out.
- If it's allergic pink eye (say, from pollen or pets), avoiding the trigger (like staying indoors on high-pollen days) might help.

Hang in there! It's usually not a huge emergency, but your comfort matters. If in doubt, a quick call to a nurse or doctor can put your mind at ease. 🧡

Figure 2. Model sample integration framework details an example of an individual's photo of their eye, the consequent deep learning model predictions, and instruction for prompt development. On the right, we see an example response generated by the EfficientNet Model and Llama 3.1 8B Turbo LLM utilizing the integration framework.

4 Conclusion

Our study demonstrates the feasibility of an integrated AI tool for classifying external eye conditions and providing condition-specific guidance. In doing so, this model addresses an ever-increasing community care need: the over-referral of benign eye conditions that can be effectively managed outside of a clinic with reassurance, education, and follow-up arrangements.

While EfficientNet-B0 achieved strong performance, we acknowledge that it functions as a black-box model and currently lacks interpretability features such as Grad-CAM to visualize areas of model attention. Incorporating such tools will be a key step toward improving transparency and building clinician trust. Similarly, although Llama 3.1 successfully generated tailored patient guidance, we recognize the absence of formal evaluation by additional ophthalmic professionals. Future work will assess the readability, clinical accuracy, and trustworthiness of this output to ensure its appropriateness for patient-facing use.

We also note the limitation of training and evaluating our system on a single public dataset. Broader validation using images across diverse demographics, such as age, ethnicity, and variable lighting conditions, will be essential to ensure fairness and generalizability. Looking ahead, we aim to test the system in real-world primary care settings, expand classification to additional conditions (e.g., styes, conjunctival hemorrhages, keratitis), and develop mobile and web-based interfaces to support community-level deployment.

By combining technical accuracy with public health relevance, our framework offers a promising model for responsible triage support in eye care, improving access, reducing the burden on specialists, and safeguarding timely care for those with vision-threatening disease.

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